

EFFECT OF TRANSVERSE NORMAL STRESS ON
THE BENDING OF THICK LAMINATED PLATES

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ABSTRACT

A bending theory is developed for symmetrically laminated, anisotropic plates which includes the effect of transverse normal stress without increasing the number of bending equations above those generated in conjunction with classical shear deformation theory. The midplane strains, however, do not vanish requiring solution to an inplane problem in order to completely describe plate behavior. Resulting field equations are based on Reissner's principle in a modified form which requires assumed interlaminar shear and normal stress distributions in addition to the inplane displacements. The effect of transverse normal stress on bending is assessed by obtaining solutions for cylindrical bending and comparing results to those obtained by neglecting the transverse normal stress terms in the governing equations. The validity of the field theory is also assessed by comparing numerical results from the approximate field theory to those obtained from exact theory of elasticity.

KEYWORDS: Anisotropy; Laminate; Laminated Plate Theory; Plates; Thick Laminate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Shear deformation theory for the bending of symmetrically laminated, anisotropic plates is based on the classic displacement field introduced by Mindlin [1]

$$u = z\psi_x(x, y), \quad v = z\psi_y(x, y), \quad w = w(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where, in the usual manner, the coordinate system is located at the plate midplane with x and y denoting the inplane coordinates and z denoting the thickness coordinate as shown in Fig.1.

Using eq. (1) in conjunction with principles of minimum potential energy, one can develop the proper constitutive relations, governing equations, and boundary conditions. In order to include the effects of transverse normal stress, however, eq. (1) is typically modified to include higher order terms in the transverse displacement (e.g. w is assumed to be quadratic in z). Such assumptions rapidly increase the number of required field equations.

FIGURE 1. Plate nomenclature

In the present paper a bending theory is developed which includes the effects of transverse normal stress without increasing the number of bending equations above those generated in conjunction with classical shear deformation theory. This is done by extending Reissner's theory [2] for homogeneous, isotropic plates to the case of laminated, anisotropic plates. The approach is based on Reissner's principle [3] in a modified form which requires assumed interlaminar shear and normal stress distributions, in addition to inplane displacements. Resulting field equations show, however, that midplane strains do not vanish, requiring solution to an inplane problem in order to completely describe plate behavior.

2. DERIVATION OF GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Consider a rectangular laminated plate of thickness h with a symmetric stacking sequence relative to the plate midplane. Each ply is constructed of an orthotropic material with the principle axis of orthotropy oriented at an arbitrary angle, θ , relative to the x -axis of the plate. The inplane displacements are assumed to be of the form

$$u = u^0(x, y) + z \psi_x(x, y), \quad v = v^0(x, y) + z \psi_y(x, y) \quad (2)$$

while the plate deflection, w , is expressed in terms of the weighted displacement

$$w^* = \frac{3}{2h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} w(x, y, z) \left[1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2\right] dz \quad (3)$$

Reissner's principle is written in terms of the variational equation $\delta\Pi = 0$. Omitting boundary and surface traction terms for simplicity, the function Π can be written in the modified form

$$\Pi = \int_V \{[\sigma_i \epsilon_i - W(\epsilon_i)] + [\sigma_j \epsilon_j - W(\epsilon_j)]\} dV \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 1, 2, 3, 6 \\ j = 4, 5 \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where, as in the usual manner, σ_i and ϵ_i denote the stress and strain components, respectively. Using conventional nomenclature, the subscripts 1, 2, and 3 here denote, x , y , and z , respectively while 4, 5, and 6 correspond to yz , xz , and xy , respectively. The ply constitutive equations are of the form

$$\sigma_i = C_{ik} \epsilon_k, \quad \epsilon_j = S_{jk} \sigma_k \quad (5)$$

where C_{ik} and S_{jk} are the stiffnesses and compliances, respectively. Substituting these relations into eq. (4) and taking the variation with respect to the stress and strain components, we obtain the following result

$$\delta\Pi = \int_V \{(\sigma_i - C_{ik} \epsilon_k) \delta\epsilon_i + (\epsilon_j - S_{jm} \sigma_{jm}) \delta\sigma_j + \sigma_i \delta\epsilon_i + \sigma_j \delta\epsilon_j\} dV \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i, k = 1, 2, 3, 6 \\ j, m = 4, 5 \end{array} \right\} \quad (6)$$

We eliminate the interlaminar normal strain ϵ_3 by utilizing the first of the constitutive relations, eq. (5), in the form

$$\sigma_i = Q_{ik} \epsilon_k + \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}} \sigma_3 \quad (i, k = 1, 2, 6) \quad (7)$$

where Q_{ij} are the reduced stiffnesses for plane stress given by the relationship

$$Q_{ik} = C_{ik} - \frac{C_{i3} C_{k3}}{C_{33}}$$

Combining eq. (7) with eq. (6) and integrating by parts we obtain, again in absence of the boundary term, the following results

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\Pi = \int_V & \{ [\sigma_i - (Q_{ik}\epsilon_j + \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}}\sigma_3)] \delta\sigma_i + (\epsilon_j - S_{km}\sigma_m) \delta\sigma_j \\
& + (\sigma_{1,1} + \sigma_{6,2} + \sigma_{5,5}) \delta u + (\sigma_{6,1} + \sigma_{2,2} + \sigma_{4,4}) \delta v \\
& (\sigma_{5,1} + \sigma_{4,2} + \sigma_{3,3}) \delta w \} dV
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where a comma denotes partial differentiation.

We now denote normal stresses, shear stresses, normal strains, and shear strains by σ_i , ϵ_i , τ_{ij} , and γ_{ij} , respectively. In order to implement eq. (8), we need to assume a distribution through the thickness for τ_{xz} , τ_{yz} , and σ_z . For simplicity we assume these stress components to be of the same form as utilized by Reissner [2] for homogeneous, isotropic plates, namely

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_{xz} &= [1 - 4(\frac{z}{h})^2] \frac{3Q_x}{2h} \\
\tau_{yz} &= [1 - 4(\frac{z}{h})^2] \frac{3Q_y}{2h} \\
\sigma_z &= \frac{1}{2} \{ [3 - 4(\frac{z}{h})^2] (\frac{z}{h})(p_1 - p_2) + (p_1 + p_2) \}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where Q_x and Q_y are the shear force resultants defined in the usual manner

$$(Q_x, Q_y) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}) dz$$

and

$$p_1 = \sigma_z(h/2), \quad p_2 = \sigma_z(-h/2)$$

These relationships are consistent with linear inplane stresses through-the-thickness for the case of homogeneous plates. It should be noted that the incorporation of σ_z in the constitutive relations, eq. (7), will induce some nonlinearity through-the-thickness with regard to the inplane stresses. This may be of little consequence, however, in obtaining macroscopic response of the laminate. Detailed local interlaminar stress distributions require integration of the equations of equilibrium in conjunction with the inplane stresses as determined from the laminated plate theory.

Substituting eqs. (2), (3), and (9) into eq. (8), we obtain the following inplane constitutive relations in terms of force resultants and moments

$$\begin{aligned} N_i &= A_{ij} \varepsilon_j + H_i (p_1 + p_2) \\ M_i &= D_{ij} \kappa_j + J_i (p_1 - p_2) \end{aligned} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} (N_i, M_i) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_i(1, z) dz, \quad (A_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij}(1, z^2) dz \\ H_i &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}} dz, \quad J_i = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}} \left(\frac{z}{h}\right) [3 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2] z dz \end{aligned}$$

We note in eq. (10) that the inplane force resultants are coupled to the lateral surface tractions. Thus, the midplane strains do not vanish in the case of the bending due to lateral load when the effects of transverse normal stress are considered. Reissner did not consider midplane strains in the development of his theory for homogeneous, isotropic plates [2]. In a similar manner we obtain the constitutive relations for the transverse shear force resultants, Q_x and Q_y , from eq. (8) with the result

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{55} & F_{45} \\ F_{45} & F_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_x + w^*_{,x} \\ \psi_y + w^*_{,y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where

$$F_{44} = \frac{R_{55}}{(R_{44} R_{55} - R_{45}^2)}, \quad F_{55} = \frac{R_{44}}{(R_{44} R_{55} - R_{45}^2)}, \quad F_{45} = -\frac{R_{45}}{(R_{44} R_{55} - R_{45}^2)}$$

and

$$R_{ij} = \frac{9}{4h^2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} S_{ij} [1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2]^2 dz \quad (i, j = 4, 5)$$

Here S_{ij} denotes the anisotropic transverse shear compliances.

The equilibrium equations in terms of force and moment resultants can be obtained from the last three terms in eq. (8) with the result

$$\begin{aligned} N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} &= 0 \\ N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} &= 0 \\ M_{x,x} + M_{xy,y} - Q_x &= 0 \\ M_{xy,x} + M_{y,y} - Q_y &= 0 \\ Q_{x,x} + Q_{y,y} + (p_1 - p_2) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

These five equations could be expressed in terms of the displacement variables u^0 , v^0 , ψ_x , ψ_y , and w^* by utilizing the constitutive relations, eqs. (10) and (11). The boundary conditions are those of classical shear deformation theory as applied to laminated plates [4].

3. CYLINDRICAL BENDING

Consider a symmetric laminate where the length in the y -direction is much longer than the x -direction. If the laminate is subjected to a lateral load which is independent of y , then the resulting deformations will be independent of y . Such cases are referred to as cylindrical bending. The displacements in eq. (2) and (3) now take the form

$$u^0 = U(x), v^0 = V(x), \psi_x = \Psi_x(x), \psi_y = \Psi_y(x), w^* = W(x) \quad (13)$$

Denoting differentiation with respect to x by a prime, the first two equilibrium equations in (12) reduce to the following

$$N_x' = 0, \quad N_{xy}' = 0 \quad (14)$$

which leads to constant values of N_x and N_{xy} . Combining eq. (13) with the constitutive relations, eqs. (10) and (11), and substituting the results into the last three equations in (12), we obtain the following bending equations

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} \Psi_x'' - F_{55} \Psi_x + D_{16} \Psi_y'' - F_{45} \Psi_y - F_{55} W' + J_1 (p_1' - p_2') &= 0 \\ D_{16} \Psi_x'' - F_{45} \Psi_x + D_{66} \Psi_y'' - F_{44} \Psi_y - F_{45} W' + J_6 (p_1' - p_2') &= 0 \\ F_{55} \Psi_x' + F_{45} \Psi_y' + F_{55} W'' + (p_1 - p_2) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

As an example we now consider a simply-supported laminate subjected to the transverse load

$$p_1 = p_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{a}, \quad p_2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

where a denotes the plate width and p_0 is a constant. For simply supported edges at $x = 0, a$:

$$\begin{aligned} N_x &= A_{11} U' + A_{16} V' + H_1 p_1 = 0 \\ N_{xy} &= A_{16} U' + A_{66} V' + H_6 p_1 = 0 \\ M_x &= D_{11} \Psi_x' + D_{16} \Psi_y' + J_1 p_1 = 0 \\ M_{xy} &= D_{16} \Psi_x' + D_{66} \Psi_y' + J_6 p_1 = 0 \\ w^* &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Since the force resultants N_x and N_{xy} are constant and must vanish at the edges, they vanish throughout the plate with the result

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \frac{(A_{66} H_1 - A_{16} H_6)}{(A_{11} A_{66} - A_{16}^2)} \left(\frac{a}{\pi}\right) p_0 \cos \pi \frac{x}{a} \\
 V &= \frac{(A_{11} H_6 - A_{16} H_1)}{(A_{11} A_{66} - A_{16}^2)} \left(\frac{a}{\pi}\right) p_0 \cos \pi \frac{x}{a}
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Note that this solution yields

$$U(a/2) = V(a/2) = 0 \tag{19}$$

A solution to eqs. (15) which satisfy the appropriate boundary conditions in eqs. (17) is of the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi_x &= A \cos \pi \frac{x}{a} \\
 \Psi_y &= B \cos \pi \frac{x}{a} \\
 w^* &= C \sin \pi \frac{x}{a}
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Substituting these functions into eqs. (15) and solving the resulting algebraic expressions for the unknown coefficients, we obtain the results

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \{F_{55} (D_{66} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{44}) (J_1 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} - 1) \\
 &+ F_{45} [D_{16} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{45} (1 - J_1 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2})] - F_{55} D_{16} J_6 \frac{\pi^4}{a^4} \} \left(\frac{a^3}{\pi^3 D_d}\right) p_0 \\
 B &= \{F_{55} (D_{16} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{45}) (J_1 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} - 1) \\
 &+ F_{45} [D_{11} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{55} (1 - J_1 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2})] - F_{55} D_{11} J_6 \frac{\pi^4}{a^4} \} \left(\frac{a^3}{\pi^3 D_d}\right) p_0 \\
 C &= \{(D_{66} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{44}) [D_{11} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{55} (1 - J_1 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2})] \\
 &- (D_{16} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{45}) [D_{16} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{45} (1 - J_1 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2})] + (F_{55} D_{16} - F_{45} D_{11}) J_6 \frac{\pi^4}{a^4} \} \left(\frac{a^4}{\pi^4 D_d}\right) p_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where

$$D_d = \{F_{55} [D_{11} (D_{66} \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + F_{44}) - D_{16}^2 \frac{\pi^2}{a^2}] - F_{45}^2 D_{11} \}$$

Inplane stresses can now be obtained from the constitutive relations, eq. (7). Interlaminar stresses can then be determined by integrating the equilibrium equations of classical theory of elasticity, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{xz} &= - \int_{-h/2}^z \sigma_{x,x}(x, \zeta) d\zeta, \quad \tau_{yz} = - \int_{-h/2}^z \tau_{xy,x}(x, \zeta) d\zeta \\ \sigma_z &= - \int_{-h/2}^z \tau_{xz,x}(x, \zeta) d\zeta\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We now consider a $[\pm 45^\circ]_S$ laminate with the following transversely isotropic ply properties

$$E_L/E_T = 14, G_{LT}/E_T = 0.533, G_{T3}/E_T = 0.323, \nu_{LT} = 0.3, \nu_{T3} = 0.55 \quad (23)$$

where the subscript L, T, and 3 denote axes parallel to the fiber, perpendicular to the fiber, and through-the-thickness of a unidirectional composite, respectively. In addition E_i , G_{ij} , and ν_{ij} denote the Young's modulus in the i th direction, the shear modulus relative to the i - j plane, and the Poisson's ratio measured by contraction in the j th direction during a uniaxial tensile test in the i th direction, respectively. These properties represent state-of-the-art unidirectional graphite/epoxy composites.

Numerical results are shown in Table 1 for the maximum deflection, which occurs at $x = a/2$, normalized by the solution as obtained from classical laminated plate theory (CLPT). The maximum deflection as determined from CLPT, denoted by w_{CLPT} , is given by the relationship

$$w_{CLPT} = \frac{a^4}{\pi^4 D_{11}} p_0 \quad (24)$$

It should be noted that the deflection w in CLPT is independent of the z coordinate. The exact elasticity solution for the plate deflection at $z = h/2, 0$, and $-h/2$ is also shown in Table 1. Exact elasticity solutions for the cylindrical bending of angle-ply plates has been obtained by Pagano [5]. This involves the application of the following equilibrium equations from classical theory of elasticity in terms of displacements

$$\begin{aligned}C_{11} u_{,xx} + C_{55} u_{,zz} + C_{16} v_{,xx} + C_{45} v_{,zz} + (C_{13} + C_{55}) w_{,xz} &= 0 \\ C_{16} u_{,xx} + C_{45} u_{,zz} + C_{66} v_{,xx} + C_{44} v_{,zz} + (C_{36} + C_{45}) w_{,xz} &= 0 \\ (C_{13} + C_{55}) u_{,xz} + (C_{36} + C_{45}) v_{,xz} + C_{55} w_{,xx} + C_{33} w_{,zz} &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (25)$$

where C_{ij} denotes the anisotropic stiffnesses. These equations are applied to each ply of the laminate and continuity conditions of appropriate stresses and displacements enforced at ply interfaces, along with the surface traction conditions

$$\tau_{xz}(\pm h/2) = \tau_{yz}(\pm h/2) = 0, \quad \sigma_z(h/2) = p_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{a}, \quad \sigma_z(-h/2) = 0 \quad (26)$$

The solution to eqs. (25) is of the variables separable form

$$u = U(z) \cos \pi \frac{x}{a}, \quad v = V(z) \cos \pi \frac{x}{a}, \quad w = W(z) \sin \pi \frac{x}{a} \quad (27)$$

The functions U , V , and W are of the form

$$(U, V, W) = (A_1, A_2, A_3) \exp s \frac{\pi}{a} x \quad (28)$$

where A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 , are constants and s is a function of the stiffnesses C_{ij} as determined from the roots of a sixth order algebraic equation. This solution satisfies the following boundary conditions at $x = 0, a$:

$$\sigma_x = \tau_{xy} = w = 0 \quad (29)$$

In Table 1 the normalized maximum deflections W^* , W^{**} , and W_E denote the present theory, the present theory with σ_z neglected ($J_1, J_6 = 0$), and the exact elasticity solution, respectively.

TABLE 1 MAXIMUM DEFLECTIONS NORMALIZED BY CLPT, [$\pm 45^\circ$]_S

a/h	W^*	W^{**}	$W_E(0)$	$W_E(h/2)$	$W_E(-h/2)$
5	1.554	1.601	1.556	1.545	1.524
10	1.146	1.157	1.146	1.140	1.139
15	1.066	1.071	1.065	1.063	1.062
20	1.037	1.040	1.037	1.035	1.035

A cursory examination of Table 1 reveals excellent agreement between the present theory and the exact elasticity solution for the deflection at the center of the plate. It is also obvious that the effect of σ_z on the maximum deflection is very small. The accuracy of the present theory and the effect of σ_z in regard to stress distributions is not investigated in the present paper and will be done in a later publication.

5. REFERENCES

1. R. D. Mindlin, "Influence of Rotatory Inertia and Shear on Flexural Motions of Isotropic, Elastic Plates," *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 18, 1951, pp. 336-343.
2. E. Reissner, "The Effect of Transverse Shear Deformation on the Bending of Elastic Plates," *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 12, 1945, pp. 69-77.

3. E. Reissner, "On a Variational Theorem in Elasticity," *Journal of Mathematics and Physics*, Vol. 29, 1950, pp. 90-97.
4. J. M. Whitney and N. J. Pagano, "Shear Deformation in Heterogenous Anisotropic Plates", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 37, 1970, pp. 1031-1036.
5. N. J. Pagano, "Influence of Shear Coupling in Cylindrical Bending of Anisotropic Plates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 4, 1970, pp. 330-343.

6. BIOGRAPHY

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